

ENVIRONMENTAL AND CHEMICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE CONDITION OF THE ENVIRONMENT AFTER THE EXPLOSION OF THE KAKHOVSKY HYDROELECTRIC POWER STATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The explosion of the Kakhovskaya hydroelectric power station caused the flooding of all towns and villages below the dam. Whole ecosystems have been destroyed, the entire territory of water development has been polluted with chemicals and fuel and lubricants. The destroyed animal and plant life of the flooded areas, the silted land and all the buildings were damaged, this is the result of the russians blowing up the Kakhovskaya HPS dam.

Keywords: Kakhovka hydroelectric power station, chemical pollution, flooding of territories, destroyed ecosystems.

Formulation of the problem. Ukraine has estimated to have lost more than 10 cubic kilometers of its most valuable resource - water. The area of the reservoir has decreased by approximately 80%. The once powerful reservoir, which provided drinking water to more than 1 million Ukrainians, was destroyed by the russians.

As a result of the terrorist attack, about 80,000 hectares of protected areas were flooded. National parks "Nizhnyodniprovskiyi", "Veliky Lug" and "Kamyanska Sich" expect a gradual and long recovery. We may forever lose endemic species of plants and animals, including the sea pike, 70% of the range of the world population of the Nordmann's mouse, up to 50% of the range of the sand fly and the white sand fly.

About 146 billion hryvnias. This is the estimated amount of damage to the environment caused by Russia's detonation of the Kakhovskaya HPS.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Environmental terrorism has long-term consequences for the population as well. The hostilities on the territory of Ukraine, which have been going on for more than a year, are causing irreparable damage to the environment. Disruption of food chains, migration processes, damage to the environment from missile or artillery strikes, this is only a small part of the colossal damage that has been done to our environment [1].

A separate situation has developed in the south of Ukraine, in the Black Sea region. Having been occupied since the first days of the war, the anthropogenic load in this area is only increasing due to active combat clashes. It is already possible to say about the critical state of the ecosystem, which has been formed there for centuries [2]. The full value of the damage from the occupation of the region is estimated only conditionally, and a full analysis of the ecological situation will be possible only after its liberation [3].

Water resources suffer quite significantly from the impact of military conflicts. The manifestation is determined by the level of aggravation of the problem and the consequences that arise in the process of water conflicts and military actions in general [4].

The main environmental disaster at the moment is the explosion of the dam of the Kakhovka hydroelectric power station, which caused the corresponding destruction of the Kakhovka reservoir and the flooding of nearby towns and villages. This environmental disaster immediately causes a large-scale impact on both the natural environment and human health [5-8].

Results.

On June 6, at 02:50, the Russian occupying forces blew up the previously mined Kakhovskaya HPS. The explosion destroyed 11 of the 28 sections of the reservoir. The approximate width of the breakthrough is 177 meters.

Fig. 1. The blown-up dam of the Kakhovskaya hydroelectric power station

All the consequences of the actual destruction of the dam can be conventionally divided into 3 stages: short-term, medium-term and long-term.

Short-term consequences

This stage is 3-4 weeks. This period will end with the formation of a more or less delineated new coastline of the Dnipro River below the Zaporizhzhya HPS up to the confluence with the Black Sea.

In general, this stage is characterized by the direct results of the undermining of the dam, namely, the rapid movement of water masses that were accumulated in the Kakhov reservoir, downstream to the mouth of the river. The main factors of impact at this time are the flooding of a significant area below the destroyed dam and a sharp drop in the level of the Kakhov reservoir, that is, the Dnieper between Zaporizhzhia and Kakhovka. Mykolaiv Oblast also experienced some flooding due to the tidal wave of the South Bug River.

In this part, it is worth highlighting the consequences of the physical impact of the shock wave of large volumes of water, water pollution due to a complex of factors and the redistribution of large volumes of water.

All natural ecosystems below the Zaporizhzhya dam were affected to one degree or another. A large part of the animals that lived below the Kakhov Dam were injured or died due to flooding. The biota of the Kakhovsky Reservoir, in particular fish, died due to a sharp drop in the water level.

The pollution of the river water of the Dnipro is associated with the lifting and transfer of silt from the bottom of the Kakhovsky Reservoir, the flooding and washing out of coastal areas, and such specific pollution as engine oils, which were used in the technological process of the dam. According to preliminary estimates, at least 150 tons of oil from the damaged dam could have entered the water. In general, the list of pollutants that have entered the water can be very large and diverse. This is microbiological pollution from dead animals and washed-out burial grounds and cemeteries, silt sediments that may contain deposits of radionuclides and heavy metals, specific chemical pollution of various types of warehouses and storage facilities in

flooded areas, including military facilities and places where fuel and lubricants are stored.

The threat to the cooling system for the Zaporizhzhia NPP should be highlighted separately. The system has its own water reservoir, which at the same time is requested from the Kakhov reservoir. Cooling is required even in the shutdown mode of the station, because the processes of nuclear fission of the fuel cannot be turned off and continue throughout the period of its use. A critical drop in the level of the coolant tank can cause emergency events at a nuclear power plant.

Medium-term consequences

Conditional period until the end of spring irrigation next year, 2024. That is, it is the next 9-10 months. During this time, a new stable coastline should be formed below the Zaporizhzhya HPP, as well as the Dnieper riverbed and water bodies in the area of its influence. During this period, it is necessary to make a new assessment of the water balance of the Dnipro River and its potential to meet social and economic needs. These time frames were chosen precisely because of the end of the annual natural life cycle of the Dnipro and its basin by the spring flood. We will see how the river, changed by the disaster, goes through this cycle.

Long-term consequences

This period will take from several years to decades. The main issue of this stage will be the further fate of the Dnipro River below Zaporizhzhia. We will not divide this stage into directions due to the significant uncertainty of future events and impacts. The main factor of further consequences will be the strategic decision regarding the Kakhovskaya HPS. Reconstruction in the form it existed before the dam was blown up will mean a gradual return of the Dnieper and the corresponding part of its basin to the state of the past decades. To what extent natural ecosystems will be able to recover, it is still impossible to say. Damaged and polluted lands will require constant monitoring and cleaning of the most polluted areas all this time. All water bodies within the influence will also need constant monitoring [9].

Due to the fact that the state in which the Dnipro was after the creation of artificial reservoirs had certain

negative ecological consequences for the river itself and its basin, it is potentially worth considering alternative options. Such options may include new technological solutions for the new Kakhovskiy Reservoir in other boundaries or volumes of water.

The most radical alternative is to refuse to build a new dam on the site of the destroyed one. This option

can be tentatively called a return to the natural state. Conditionally - because the natural and climatic condition of this territory of Ukraine has changed significantly since the construction of the HPS. The evaluation of options should include all aspects: economic, technological, environmental and even tourism and aesthetics [10].

Fig. 2. Flooded cities as a result of the explosion of the Kakhovskaya hydroelectric power station

Blowing up the Kakhovskaya HPP «is a blow to global food security», because it will affect the irrigation system in the South of Ukraine. This will have an impact, because the irrigation canals will not work as before, because these hydrotechnical structures were designed for a certain water level of the Dnipro, for the amount of water that enters, in particular, through the Kakhov reservoir. Now the Kakhov reservoir will be liquidated, so the irrigation systems will be dry and empty. And this will continue to be a huge problem for irrigated agriculture in the south of the Kherson region.

Up to 280 tons of lubricants, which were in the HPS units, created a surface film and will settle to the bottom of the flooded area.

For southern Ukraine and the Black Sea basin, this is a real ecological disaster. Now, on the first day after the detonation, we can observe «quick» destructive consequences — this is a catastrophic and partial flooding of the territories. It is possible that later we will begin to learn about the deaths of people and animals. The numbers of these destructions will be impressive, but they will not illustrate all the possible damage that we will have to face [11].

There is no engine room of the Kakhovskaya HPS at all. If we take the sum of all aggregates as a minimum, then there should be somewhere around 280 tons. In any case, it's a lot. Spilled fuel and lubricating materials and lubricating and cooling fluids form a surface film and settle in bottom sediments.

Secondary consequences: epidemiological risks, spillage of chemicals, pollution with nitrogen and phosphorus compounds.

Sweeping everything in its path, the water is contaminated with chemicals from industrial enterprises, mixed with sewage, etc. Epidemiological risks and risks of water pollution are multiplying.

The flooding of cesspools, sewage networks, drainage and other treatment facilities will inevitably lead to water pollution (however, this is not the worst case scenario).

Given the specifics of the agro-industrial area and the unexpected nature of the events, warehouses and other facilities for the storage of chemical plant protection agents and fertilizers were flooded. This is already bad, especially for fertilizers. It is extremely difficult to assess the damage.

Flooding and tidal flow will inevitably lead to secondary pollution of the water mass with suspended substances, biogenic elements (compounds of nitrogen and phosphorus).

The processes of bird nesting and fish spawning have been interrupted, the unique plants of southern Ukraine have been destroyed.

The consequences of the undermining of the Kakhovskiy Reservoir dam will have a global ecological character for the Black Sea region. The unique natural ecosystem of the floodplain of the Dnieper from Novaya Kakhovka to the Dnipro-Buzka estuary, which is more than 80,000 hectares of the «Lower Dnipro» natural territory, was actually destroyed [12].

A man-made disaster of this scale significantly exceeds the adaptive capacity of the swimming biotope. Hundreds of islets, areas of unique floodplain forest, flooded meadows and steppe areas of the lower slopes with all the inhabitants were washed into the sea.

The breeding season of birds, the period of nesting and spawning of fish, as well as hundreds of species of living organisms, of which 71 species of animals and 32 species of plants are included in the World Red List of the IUCN, as well as the European Red List, the Red Book of Ukraine and the Red List of the Kherson Region, are under threat.

Possible delayed consequences: dust storms, rising temperatures, turning the area into a desert

It is also important that the reservoir of Kakhovskaya HPS was an important ecological environment and a source of fresh water for many species of plants and animals.

If a huge sandy bottom is opened, we will get a new desert with all the climatic consequences: a decrease in precipitation, dust storms, a rise in temperature in the region. And accordingly, there is a greater risk of drought in the fields of central and southern Ukraine. The lack of water in the Kakhovsky Sea will lead to the drying of the fields of southern Ukraine with further desertification.

So there will be environmental, social, economic, sanitary and other consequences, significant, but in the long term.

Limited use of water for residents of cities that live higher up the cascade of the Dnipro reservoirs

The situation will not affect the quality of water in the Dnipro and Kremenchuk South-Ukrainian reservoirs, but a large number of populated cities will switch to decentralized water supply in emergency conditions. This applies to Dnipro, Zaporizhzhia, Kryvyi Rih:

For some time, the supply of water to field irrigation systems in the Kherson, Dnipropetrovsk, and Zaporizhzhia regions may stop, mainly on occupied lands. Many cities and villages that consume it from the Kakhovsky Canal risk being left without drinking water, in particular occupied Berdyansk.

The situation is the same in Crimea. Due to the explosion of the Kakhovskaya HPS, Crimea lost its most important irrigation channel and was virtually left without a source of fresh water.

Conclusions. The explosion destroyed 11 of the 28 sections of the reservoir. The approximate width of the breakthrough is 177 meters. Blowing up the Kakhovskaya HPS is a blow to global food security, because it will affect the irrigation system in the South of Ukraine. This will have an impact, because the irrigation canals will not work as before, because these hydrotechnical structures were designed for a certain water level of the Dnipro, for the amount of water that enters, in particular, through the Kakhov reservoir.

Up to 280 tons of lubricants, which were in the HPS units, created a surface film and will settle to the bottom of the flooded area. Sweeping everything in its path, the water is contaminated with chemicals from industrial enterprises, mixed with sewage, etc. Epidemiological risks and risks of water pollution are multiplying.

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